

NEW EDUCATION POLICY 2020: IMPORTANCE OF INTERNSHIPS DURING HIGHER EDUCATION AND ITS NEED IN THE PRESENT AND FUTURE

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Abstract:

The New Education Policy 2020 passed by Union Cabinet emphasises on holistic and multidisciplinary education system. Multidisciplinary education means combining different disciplines in one education institution. Many new ideas are presented in the policy one of which being internships at higher level education. Internship is a foundation of a student's career after their basic education is completed. It acts as a bridge from coursework to practical world. Internships are like playing test match before playing a real game, the candidate gets to know the work environment, job expectancy, leadership, and work ethics and so on. The objective of this study is to bring light on the topic of internship, the importance of internship discussed in the New Education Policy, and to know the present and future need of internship in education system. To study the objective of this research paper a survey was employed to 53 participants. The questionnaire was prepared to know the opinion of participants on internships. The comments and suggestions made by the participants are discussed in the research paper. The result analysis of the data shows a strong need of internship programs. The overall results and finding have shown immediate demand of internship opportunities in India. With the growing demand for skilled based job, it is essential that organizations move towards hiring interns and mould them into skilled labour.

Keyword: new education policy, internship, higher education, skills development, employment

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Introduction:

The New Education Policy 2020 passed by Union Cabinet emphasises on holistic and multidisciplinary education system. Holistic and multidisciplinary approach means students can learn arts, science, technology, history, physical education, music, dance, drama, human values, ethics, and morality and so on at the same time. In this policy new 5+3+3+4 structure is introduced. Many additional changes will be made to the existing structure of education system. The policy has focused on including all extra-curricular activity in the daily academic work, making it multidisciplinary.

The new higher education system focuses on developing good thoughtful and well-rounded creative individuals. Higher education plays an extremely important role in promoting human as well as societal well-being and in developing India as envisioned in its Constitution - a democratic, just, socially-conscious, cultured, and humane nation upholding liberty, equality, fraternity, and justice for all. Higher education significantly contributes towards sustainable livelihoods and economic development of the nation (New Education Policy 2020). According to NEP, the higher education is of four years it includes that a student can choose the subjects which they want to study and the students can do their major and minor in any subjects. As a part of new education system students will be provided opportunities

for internships with local industry and research internships with academicians and research scholars. It will help the students to choose their career path.

India, a country with majority of young population and with less employment rates; it is important to include skill based curriculum in the formative years of the students. (India Skill Report 2019) It is reported that 84% of Indian students prefer Internship programs, however only 37% of organizations provide internship opportunities. Internships will help students to hunt jobs. And with added internship experience the process of procuring employment will get easier.

This research paper discusses about how internship is presented in the policy and how it is important in the future and also in the present scenario.

Literature review:

(Sweitzer & King, 2014) In this book the authors discuss about successful and rewarding experience of the internship program. What are the difficulties faced by the students as well as the teachers during internship program is briefly discussed in the book. This book majorly focused on how the internship helped the students to understand the need of the clients specifically who are involved in the service sector.

(Patacsil & Tablatin, 2017) Students perceived that hard skills were very important while industry perceived hard skills were somewhat important. The study suggests that the university should enrich the soft skills and entry level hard skills component in the curriculum. The students selected for this study had strong background of the needs of the company based on their internship experience.

(Sharir, et al., 2016) In this study the researcher concluded that internship program conducted by the university have positive effect on the future of the interns. The overall results and findings have shown positive effect on learners, academics and university.

By having this internship programme, the students will have practical skills that can boost their understanding of issues which are significant to a particular work (Furco, 1996) (Hughes, 1998) and enhance employability, provide the students with real expectations of interns, furnish satisfaction of the internship experience and giving internship prerequisites as predictors of internship success (Knouse & Fontenot, 2008).

Internship:

Internships can play an important role in helping students make the good career choices (Brooks, 1995). Exposure to real-world problems and issues that are usually not well defined or assessed as those normally contained in textbooks is a valuable, out-of-the-classroom learning opportunity (Coco, 2000). Experience, both intellectual and emotional, is the raw material of the internship. You will be learning mostly through experience, although you may engage in some traditional academic activities (H & King, 2009).

Internship brings forth many advantages that interns can benefit from such as improvements in their career direction, job preparedness of the interns, the interns' marketability, job expectations, interpersonal skills and leadership (Cook, Parker, & Pettijohn, 2000) that is basically highlighting the profound benefits of the enhancement of work ethics and life skills of interns (Abdullah, Peng, J., & Singh, 2019).

The purpose of internship is to provide a planned transition from classroom to the job, and internships are a natural bridge between college and the work world. Students, educational institutions and businesses believe that internships complement the student's academic work (Farinelli & Mann, 1994). Regardless of what profession you enter, or even

whether you enter a profession at all, the internship is an opportunity for you to learn some of what will help you participate fully and productively in your community (H & King, 2009).

Internship discussed in New Education Policy 2020:

As a part of holistic education, all the students will be given opportunity to intern in their choice of field so they get hands on training of what their future will consist. Students can intern with local industries, business, artists, craft persons, etc. and also research interns will work under academics and scholars to get practical knowledge and as a by-product improve their employability. In all the levels of learning, experimental learning will be adopted whether it is arts related or sport related. Experimental learning will close the gap between class work and practical knowledge. Higher education institutions will take steps to make curriculum more inclusive and increase employability potential of students. The aim of Internships is meeting skill requirement of 21st century, which is one of the goal of this policy.

Importance and Need of Internship:

1. Clarity of future career: Most students have never actually worked in the field of interest. Internship provide this opportunity to test drive their interests. Internships enable students to gain some practical knowledge of the work and then select their remaining courses more wisely. It will motivate the students to master the subject. (Hergert, 2009) Found that students place a great value on the internship experience and it is particularly true when the internship has a direct connection to their ultimate career goals. The students will learn about the organizational structure and operations about the place by observing the conditions of employment in the past and the future. By analysing above characteristics the intern can decide whether they want to choose this job as a profession. Moreover, if not then what are the other opportunities.
2. Developing essential skills: Learning from coursework to work world transition can be difficult. While interning in any work place student can learn how the daily life would be if they choose this job as a career. They also provide an opportunity to learn specific job related skills that are not taught in traditional programs (Garavan & Murphy, 2001). Interns can develop skills like Expertise, Working as a team, Confidence, Freedom of choice, Sense of Accomplishment, etc. When such skills are developed the interns can easily acquire any related job of their choice and job hunting gets easier.
3. Connection of coursework and practical knowledge: Other studies have found that internships can make students more ambitious (Pedro, 1984) and can help ease the transition from school to work (Paulson & Baker, 1999). The business world becomes a laboratory for students to see how the material they have learned in the classroom related to the practice of business (Hergert, 2009).
4. Better employment Opportunities: Internships also open many doors to networking opportunities which helps the student's job hunting process. Students are often motivated to seek out internships as a means for securing eventual permanent employment. Prior research indicates that this does indeed work (Callanan, 2004). Internship programs also hold benefits for the field supervisors and sponsoring organizations, such as providing motivated workers at no or relatively low cost to an organization and furnishing the opportunity to train possible future employees for the organization (Seibert, Hart, Sypher, & Davenport, 1989). Also while interning with an employer the transition from internship to job becomes easier.
5. Understanding the values and ethics: In the academic curricula students are taught about work ethics and morals but when they are out in the real life situation they get to put those values in use. During coursework students construct

their intellect but during internship student shape their characters.

Objective:

The objective of this study is to shine light on the topic of internship. The importance of internship discussed in the New Education Policy. Moreover, to know the present and future need of internship in education system.

Research Methodology

A survey was employed to collect the data for this study. A questionnaire was distributed on online link through Social media. The Survey contained multiple choice questions which included the following: demographic background, whether they have participated in any internship program, what are their opinion on internships, and what are the benefits of internships and any open ended comment regarding internships were analysed and concluded accordingly. The sample size of the data is 53 participants.

Analysis of the data:

a) Demographic background:

i) Gender wise distribution

Table 1 Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	24	45.3%
Female	29	54.7%
Other	0	-
Total	53	100%

As shown in the above Table 1 majority of participants are female with 54.7%, while rest are 24 male participants (45.3%).

ii) Age wise distribution

Table 2 Agedistribution

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 18	0	-
18-20	4	7.5%
21-25	38	71.7%
26-30	8	15.1%
31-35	3	5.7%
Above 35	0	-
Total	53	100%

In Table 2, the highest participants are in the age group of 21-25 i.e. 71.7%. Whereas age group of 26-30 are the second highest with 15.1% participants (8 participants).

b) Participation in any internship program

Table 3 Participation in internship program

Participation in internship program	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	29	54.7%
No	24	45.3%
Total	53	100%

In Table 3, it is shown that 29 participants i.e. 54.7% have interned with an employer. While the rest 45.3% have not participated in any internship program.

i) The participants answered- Yes

Figure 1 Reasons to participate in Internship Program

The above Figure 1, represents the participant's reason to partake in internship program. The majority of participants did the program to graduate or to complete a certificate. Second reason to participate in program is to get monetary benefit from the employer. Some participants voluntarily partake in the program where as rest of the participants participated for other motives.

ii) The participants answered- No

Table 4 Reason to not participate in Internship Program

Reason to not participate in internship program	Frequency	Percentage
There is no internship program	10	41.7%
Not interested	5	20.8%
Other	9	37.5%
Total	24	100%

Table 4, represents the participants reasons to not intern in any program. Out of 24 participants 10 i.e. 41% found no internship program, whereas 9 participants i.e. 37.5% didn't participate in internship because of other reasons.

c) Benefits of internship opportunity:

Figure 2 Benefits of Internship Program

From the above Figure 2, we can observe that the major benefit of internship is gaining experience and developing skills. Choosing career path is also one of the main benefits of internship, this benefit acts like a trial and error period until the participant find its field of interest. The other benefit is to get the job opportunity with the same employer, which can be a positive factor if the company in which the participant is working takes interns into full time employees.

d) Opinion on Internship program incorporation

Table 5 Opinion on Internship Program

Opinion on internship program incorporation	Frequency	Percentage
Internship program should is incorporated	50	94.3%
Internship program should not be incorporated	-	-
Maybe	3	5.7%
Total	53	100%

The above table shows the opinion of participants on incorporation of internship program. Almost all the participants' i.e.94.3% feel that internship program should be incorporated during or after education. While 3 participants are not sure.

e) Comments and suggestions on internships in India

<i>Comments</i>	-Internship helps to develop personality, improves working capacity and also gives real
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	<p>understanding between theory and its application in reality.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Internships provide opportunity to fresher student. -Internship give practical experience of what we study. - Internships provide good platform for students with industry ready skills. -It helps student enhance their skill and confidence.
<p><i>Suggestions</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More Internship schemes should be introduced. - After education internships should be made compulsory. - Organizations should present new schemes which include internships. -Colleges should provide internship opportunity. - Stipends/Salary given during internships should be increased.

Conclusion:

In India, Internship program are very restricted. Only some professions acquire interns because it is mandatory to get a degree or certification by completing a certain period of time. As of today, Chartered Accountant, Architecture, MBA schools, MBBS and so on are the only profession in which internships are mandatory. Introducing internship programs in higher education level will increase the chance of employability to students and also it will motivate them to choose a correct career path. This research learnt the importance of internship program. The overall results and finding have shown immediate need of internship opportunity in India. With the growing demand for skilled based job, it is essential that organizations move towards hiring interns and mould them into skilled labour. Then the gap of graduates and unemployment can decrease.

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